

ANALYSIS OF THE NATURE OF CHARACTERS IN THE TALE "WHO IS THE ONE THAT NOT EIGHTEEN"

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Abstract. *In this article, the spirituality of the heroes in the story of the writer Shukur Kholmiraev "Who is the one that not 18", worldview, as well as how social problems and problems of that time are depicted, as well as the unique character of the heroes are considered. The role of the story in the education of modern youth and how much the issue of reading influenced the moral state of the heroes of the story are considered.*

Keywords: *great writer, trend, heroes' worldview, artistic analysis, artistic image, artistic concept, creative process, national traditions, writer's fantasy, hero's inner world, artistic skill, love, consequence, mistake and fate. Sangardak, Mount Yetim, Mount Farkhad, Ketmon Chopti.*

Shukur Kholmiraev stands out among the generation of writers who have made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature since the 60s of the twentieth century and continued to create fruitfully in the 21st century.

In the last quarter of this century, Shukur Kholmiraev further enriched the traditions of Uzbek storytelling of the 20th century. A number of his works, which raised Uzbek storytelling to a new level, were rightfully called large-scale examples of this genre. The stories of Shukur Kholmiraev are glorious manifestations of ordinary pain. Most of the writer's characters are ordinary people who, at first glance, have no interest in their homeland, their nation, or all of humanity. But the writer's gaze was so sharp that he was able to see, describe, and show the pain of the nation, the homeland, and the people behind this inviolability. In the writer's stories, we almost never find characters, dry exhortations, or standard phrases. He always tried to create new images. He tried to find unique innovations in the compositional construction of the work.

In this regard, he did not hesitate to experiment and often achieved success. An Uzbek man wrote down the inexplicable aspects of his dreams, in most cases his hidden suffering, the evolution of his psyche. These characters are not like the characters of other writers: sometimes they are beautiful, sometimes rude, sometimes representatives of a small environment. But the inner world of all of them is unique, spiritually deep, humane, alive and vital people who do not retreat from their beliefs and think accordingly. These heroes put their personality, nationality, land and culture, religion above all else. They fight for justice and truth. However, the hero will never become arrogant and justify himself for this purpose. They are not attractive on the outside, but often attractive, willing and loving on the inside. Shukur Kholmiraev's stories are focused on the artistic analysis of unresolved problems in life, in the human heart. The writer's heroes do not chew the idea of the work, artistic discoveries in the mouth of the reader. The work does not finish drawing or improve the characters of the unfortunate, who have not found the right path in life, unpleasant or scoundrels. He leaves them as they are in life, to the extent that his artistic concept is realized, and submits them to the reader's judgment. A great work of art is a true reflection of life. That is why the reader finds himself, sees his reflection, worries, rejoices, cries, suffers. In a word, he lives with the heroes of the play. This is how Shukur Kholmiraev's story "Who is the

one that not 18" gets into the reader's heart. This story brought fame to the twenty-five-year-old writer among Uzbek readers. This story, dedicated to the problems of love, fate, loss and fate, the desire for life and the education of the character of young people, has been loved by young people for almost sixty years.

Many works are devoted to these issues in both Uzbek and world literature. But the story "Who is the one that not 18" attracts attention not only with the plot, the fates of the heroes, but also with the fact that the light emanating from their beating hearts resonates in a unique way under the pen of the writer in sincere tones, like love itself. Although the title of the story clearly indicates that the work is about love, the fact that the first events of the story tell about the experiences of half-children filling the reader with reflections.

"Who is the one that not 18..." is one of the author's autobiographical works. The author's half-brother Tora and family events served as the reason for writing the story. Brother Shukur spoke about these events with pain, and I felt that he was writing something about those days. Because the writer usually talked a lot about the works he planned to write or finish, and watched the "reaction" of the interlocutor. At that time, I could not imagine that a woman whose husband was in the army could run away with someone, and, frankly, I felt sorry for Brother Tora. Maybe because I read these details later in the essay "This Man is My Teacher, I am a student", each image and detail seemed different to me, it created the impression of some kind of fairy tale about loved ones. For example, Jamshid-Shukur Kholmiraev, Tilov-Tora's brother, Zainabkhan-the writer's mother, Jalolov-Orzikul-the wrestler, Muslima's grandmother-mother Rukhsat will become the reader's closest interlocutors in the work. Let's start with Momo. In the work, the grandmother's past is described as follows: "Grandmother Muslima was twenty-five years old, and she was left with two children - a daughter, Zainab Khan, and a son, Abdugarim. (Her husband died fighting the enemies.) At that time, these places were barren land. After that, the old woman no longer engaged in agriculture and devoted the rest of her life to raising her two sons and gardening for them. At night, she fed her children with spinning wheels. Over the years, both the garden and the children became people. But one of his children followed in his father's footsteps (he died fighting the Nazi invaders). And Zainab Khan came out, a flying bird, not at all like Grandma Muslima? He still goes to Tashkent to study, still wanders from village to village as a soldier for a month, in the old war years if he was at home for a day, it was not a week. In Sanjartog he was the leader of those who collected yellow flowers. He was always faithful to the old woman and left this garden" [8, 9].

In this work, the writer remembers his real father Fayzulla Kholmiraev with longing and melancholy. Jamshid (Shukur) rarely heard the word father. But he knew that his father went to fight the "fascists" and would return one day. Jamshid was little and was lying in his crib when his father left: "The day he left, his aunt carried Jamshid out. His father threw Jamshid into the sky and said: "I will come. You will grow up". His hair was curly. But Jamshid's is not curly. Soft, smooth, like mother's" [8, 29].

The events of the work mainly take place in the courtyard of Muslima's grandmother. The writer describes the times of his youth with great longing and love, so that after reading it is impossible not to recognize the writer's memory. Jamshid's childhood, Zainabkhan's visit to the Pobeda collective farm as a fellow traveler, the events of "Uncle Rais" - Dzhalalov becoming Jamshid's father, Tilov's entry into Jamshid's world, the relationship between half-brothers and sisters, and the state of old Muslima. This is not the writer's creative fantasy, but an artistic

reflection of real events. In general, the writer's childhood and youth were spent in "Who is the one that not 18...".

According to the story, old Muslima was attracted by her new fiancé Dzhalalov, and she was surprised: "Isn't it a man with a house and a good reputation who came as a fiancé?" [8, 36] - he said to himself. And Jalolov was carefree, behaved freely, simply moved from one house to another. Finally, Muslims's grandmother thought: "He has many verbs," and her son-in-law liked her" [8, 36].

The book "Who is the one that not 18..." was published in 1965. In the 4th issue of the magazine "Shark yztyzi" for 1966, an article by literary scholar Laziz Kayumov "Thoughts on our fiction of 1965" was published. Analyzing one after another the works published in 1965, L. Kayumov says the following about "Who is the one that not 18": "The story of Shukur Kholmiraev "Who is the one that not 18..." is a hope for the gallery of images in our literature, Jamshid, Tilov and cute and realistic characters are added. As an example of their relationships and destinies, the author naturally described the first steps at the beginning of an independent life, the mistakes during that period, first love and its charm. Sh. Kholmiraev mastered the skill of psychological observation and in this work was able to convincingly describe the inner world of young people. In his style there is a strong desire for vitality and naturalness, and this is good" [7, 92].

In the first issue of the magazine "Shark Yztyziri" for 1969, an article by critic Norboy Khudoyberganov "Fruits of inspiration" was published. When analyzing a number of works, the critic also touched upon the story "Who is the one that not 18" and expressed the following opinion: it is difficult to say that he acts based on the logic of life" [7, 92].

Adhering to his own style, the critic evaluates the work according to the model of a positive and negative hero. The critic, who saw signs of egoism in Jamshid, said: "Did the writer look at the hero he loved and admired with the eyes of truth?", he poses the question crosswise and accuses the author of describing egoism with goodwill. Sh. Kholmiraev's opinion about his work: "In general, Shukur Kholmiraev shows that he is able to sensitively resolve complex, sometimes illogical situations in human language. He talks about life events that he knows well, feels and acquires social meaning, tries to say what he wants to say with excitement and emotion, and thereby arouse excitement in the hearts of others," he concludes. But some of the teacher's comments at the end of the article are controversial. According to N. Khudoyberganov, "any passion, any warmth is not the fruit of artistic and literary talent. Momentary sensations, emotions, generally being under influence, excitement are inherent in every person, but excitement, being under influence alone does not give the right to create ... or you can create prose works, but such works cannot be a big event" [7,93].

It seems to me that these opinions of an attentive critic who loves debates are addressed not to artists, but to other professions. The uniqueness and mystery of the world of creation and man is that it does not obey the established laws and norms of existing life. Why do you say that, by the standards of N. Khudoyberganov, if subtract passion, temperature, emotions, influence, excitement, arousal, instantaneous burning, burns, then the reader will be able to read without stopping, and this work would not have been created? Therefore, we cannot yet get used to the demands of N. Khudoyberganov.

In the story, the writer tries to reveal the excruciating suffering left by the war in the destinies of people, especially in the interpretation of the image of Grandmother Muslima.

Grandmother Muslima was only twenty-five years old when her husband died fighting the enemy in the war. She is left with two children: daughter Zainabkhan and son Abdukarim. It is shown that the war left the young man an early widow, orphans who have not yet been satiated with their father's love, and using the example of one family, brought a dark day on the head of an entire nation. The reader, reading the grief of Grandmother Muslima, whom the war separated from her loved ones not once, but twice, involuntarily condemns the war. Abdukarim, the only son of Grandmother Muslima, died in battle with the fascists, and the work skillfully shows how this poor old woman did not complain about her fate and lived by her own will. In another place, Jamshid's story about "Iskander's campaign" [8, 36], which Gadzhiyev heard from his teacher, shows the negative consequences of the war. In the process of reading this story, the reader will witness how well the writer knew the history of the region in which he lived. In particular, an attempt was made to convey to the reader in the language of the characters the history of such toponyms as Sanjarbek, Yetim tog, Farkhod tog, Ketmon chopti.

We can see our point in the following passage from the work:

"Why don't they call this ridge Farkhad?" asked one of the children.

"Why is the peak called Ketmon Chopti?" asked the second.

Gadzhiyev shook his round belly from his palms and looked back.

"They say that Farkhad climbed this mountain for water. At that time, our Sangar was a dry desert. Farkhad hit the mountain with his hoe and when he looked down, he saw a large river flowing down. Where did this river come from? Farkhad did not know that these were mats spread by an old woman. In Farkhad's eyes, he looked like a river. Then Farkhad made a deal with Yasuman, saying that he had won the deal, and committed suicide. The name of the mountain is Farkhad. The place where Farkhad hit the hoe is Ketmon Chopti. If you really go there and look, it looks like a hoe. I am like a large gorge. It is interesting that the source of the river that feeds our village is located here. As if a hoe is spreading out of the ground" [8, 61].

If we carefully observe the main characters of the story, we will feel with our hearts the psyche of the heroes of the love triangle. This is the merit of the writer. The difference between this story and other works that glorify love is that the character traits of the heroes in it, their worldview and spirituality go back to the books they have read. Shukur Kholmirezayev invites the reader to carefully observe the sequence of events through the plot of the unification of the destinies of two orphans: the marriage of Jamshid's mother Zainabkhan to Dzhaliolov's father Tilov and the fact that children of different blood become brothers and sisters. From time immemorial, people have had a negative attitude towards "stepmother" and "stepfather". But in this story, Shukur Kholmirezayev refuted the negative assessment of these words and showed that they should be treated positively. Zainab Khan said that the "stepmother" always expects bad things from "stepfathers" or condemns them and is embodied through Jalolov.

The work mentions the names of several books and the characters in them. Calling each other imitating the characters of the play, children similar to these characters, especially Umida's happiness, like Katerina, Jamila and Nina, were subjected to oppression, humiliation, as a result, one threw himself into the water, another drank poison, and one fell ill with madness from the fact that he dreams of playing ghost characters, and then for some reason feels bitter and personally wants to be like them, skillfully depicted, the hero's life also ends in the same way as the life of this hero.

A great work of art is a true reflection of life. Therefore, the student finds himself in it, sees his reflection, worries, rejoices, cries, suffers. In a word, he lives with the heroes of the work. This is how this story by the famous writer Shukur Kholmiraev penetrates the reader's heart.

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